

PRODUCTION OF THE JOSHI EFFECT IN OXYGEN UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE. PART I. INFLUENCE OF THE EXCITING POTENTIAL AND THE GAS PRESSURE

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The Joshi effect, Δi , an instantaneous and reversible photo-variation (usually, diminution) of the discharge current i in gases, has been studied in oxygen in the range 10-500 mm. Hg (p) and excited by ozoniser discharges over 0.5 to 6 kilo-volts (V) of 50 cycles frequency. 'Threshold potential' V_m , at which i increases rapidly with V , varies sensibly linearly with p . Well below V_m , Δi is not detected. Above V_m , Δi at constant p first increases with V and then decreases. The relative effect, % Δi , is a maximum near V_m , and diminishes thereafter. The potential distribution in respect of both Δi and % Δi is flat at higher p , which is significant for the pressure-dependence of the mechanism of Δi . The authors' observation under a wide range of conditions of up to 50% current decrease in oxygen under but visible light suggests that the Joshi effect is not a special reaction limited to excited halogens. The generality of results are in accord with Joshi's theory of this phenomenon.

Joshi and Deshmukh (*Nature*, 1941, 147, 806) and Deshmukh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 211), using special large discharge tubes, intense radiations of short wave-length, and current-sensitive indicators observed the Joshi effect, Δi , in oxygen excited by 'silent discharge'; Δi corresponded to about 4%. This was confirmed by the results of Joshi and Cherian (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1942, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 56), and Mohanty and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1947, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. Nos. 14, 15; 1948, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. Nos. 13, 19; *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. Nos. 35, 36). Apart from these preliminary observations, the entire work on this new phenomenon has been confined to halogens, especially chlorine which shows Δi to the largest extent. It was of interest therefore to investigate in some detail its production in oxygen.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The apparatus used (Fig. 1) consisted essentially of a discharge vessel formed with two co-axial glass tubes fused together as in a Siemens' ozoniser. This was connected on one hand through taps T_1 and T_2 , a cooling spiral S and tap T_3 to a reservoir R of pure oxygen; and to a mercury manometer M, and Töpler on the other. The whole or any desired part of the apparatus could be connected to the Töpler by manipulation of taps T_1 to T_3 . The entire all-glass assembly was tested for a satisfactory vacuum for atleast 48 hours before commencing any given series of experiments. Oxygen was obtained by heating carefully pure potassium permanganate in the hard glass tube, H, plugged with glass-wool. It was dried by leading slowly through a train of tubes containing respectively fused calcium chloride, potassium hydroxide and phosphorus pentoxide. The first lot of the evolved gas was rejected by pumping off with the Töpler through tap T_3 , taps T_1 and T_2 being closed. A given series of Δi observations was commenced after the entire apparatus was washed repeatedly with purified oxygen

subjected to discharge in the ozoniser and tōplered off. This served to eliminate any traces of adsorbed impurities. Before admitting into the ozoniser at a desired pressure, oxygen from R was first led slowly through the spiral S, cooled by liquid air in the Dewar flask, D. This removed, by freezing out, any condensible impurities in the gas. The pressure of the gas in the ozoniser was observed with the manometer, M. To prevent rise in temperature of the gas in the ozoniser due to heat produced under discharge, water at a temperature within $\pm 1^\circ$ was circulated through a glass jacket (not shown in Fig. 1) surrounding the ozoniser system.

Two ozonisers A and B were used. They had the following dimensions :

	A (Monax glass)	B (Indian soft soda glass)
External diameter of the outer tube in mm	22.5	20.5
Internal " " " "	20	17.5
External " " inner " "	15	14
Internal " " " "	12.5	11
Thickness of the glass wall	1.25	1.5
Inter-electrode distance	2.5	1.75
Length of the electrode space	965	432

FIG. 1

Production of the Joshi effect in oxygen

The electrical connections are shown in Fig. 1. A single phase alternating current of 50 cycles frequency was obtained from a 1 kW rotary converter worked off 220 volt, D. C. mains. Its output was fed to the primaries of a high-tension transformer. The primary current and voltage were observed by an ammeter, A and a voltmeter, V' respectively. The ozoniser terminals, represented by a 10% solution of sodium chloride inside the inner tube and in the bath surrounding the outer tube of the ozoniser, were connected to the secondaries of the high-tension transformer. The P. D. across the secondaries V applied to the ozoniser was varied, and kept constant within 1% at a desired value, by hand regulation of the primary voltage with the potentiometric arrangement shown (Fig. 1).

The discharge current i flowing through the ozoniser A was detected by a mirror galvanometer G, actuated by a Cambridge vacuo-junction V. J., the connections being through α, α (Fig. 1); that flowing through the ozoniser B was passed through the primaries of a Bell type 3:1, step-up iron-core transformer by making connections through β, β (α, α having been disconnected). The secondaries of the transformer were connected to the plates and the cathodes of a (RCA) 6H6 double diode through G which was suitably shunted. The filament of the valve was heated by a current of 270 mA obtained from a 6 volt storage cell.

The source of irradiation consisted of a battery of 200 watt (glass) bulbs run at 200 volts. The current in the dark i_b was noted with the source of light on, and the shutter in position. On moving the shutter, the discharge vessel was flooded with light, and the current diminished immediately to i_c . On shutting off the light, it increased similarly to its original value, i_b .

Ozoniser A, filled with purified oxygen at various pressures in the range of 10 to 250 mm. Hg, was subjected to different alternating potentials V varied over 0.5--4 kV (r. m. s.). In Table I, which represents but one typical series of results with this ozoniser, are shown the discharge current in dark i_b , that under irradiation i_c , the net Joshi effect $\Delta i = i_b - i_c$, and the proportional effect expressed as a percentage, i.e., $100\Delta i/i_b$; since vacuo-junction was the detector, the current values are in square root of the corresponding galvanometer deflections. Table II represents another group of typical data with ozoniser B in the pressure range of 50 to 500 mm. and excited by 0.5 to 6 kV; the current values are in galvanometer deflections, the A. C. indicator being a diode. In Figs. 2 and 3 are shown the V- i characteristics for oxygen gas in the ozonisers A and B respectively for different pressures, in dark (continuous curves), and under irradiation (discontinuous curves). These curves show the essence of the phenomenon, viz., that i produced due to various applied V diminishes as a result of irradiation. The continuous curves at the bottom of Figs. 2 and 3 illustrate the variation of the net effect Δi with V; curves shown by dots and dashes show the corresponding variation of $\% \Delta i$. In Fig. 4 are plotted the 'threshold potentials' V_m (*vide infra*) for oxygen in ozoniser B at various gas pressures.

TABLE I

Potential variation of the Joshi effect in oxygen at different gas pressures with vacuo-junction detection.

(Ozoniser A)

Temp. = 19°—21°. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec. Source of irradiation = Three 200 watt (glass) bulbs run at 200 volts, and 22 cm. from A.

Pressure of oxygen in mm.											
	21. V=0.67.			21. V=0.8.				21 V=0.93.			
	10.	31.	43.	10.	31.	43.	10.	31.	43.	10.	43.
i_D	4.12	3.74	2.45	3.61	5.39	5.1	3.74	3.46	5.2	6.25	5.66
i_L	2.24	2.45	1.58	2.24	3.61	3.74	2.45	2.65	3.87	4.58	4.00
Δi	1.88	1.29	0.87	1.37	1.78	1.36	1.29	0.81	1.33	1.67	1.66
% Δi	45.6	34.5	35.5	38	33.0	26.7	34.5	23.4	25.6	26.7	29.3

Pressure of oxygen in mm.								
	10.	21. V=1.07		43.	10.	21. V=1.2		43.
	10.	31.	43.	10.	31.	43.	10.	43.
i_D	3.61	5.39	6.93	6.33	3.81	5.57	7.35	6.78
i_L	3.00	4.24	5.1	4.8	3.46	4.58	5.57	5.29
Δi	0.61	1.15	1.83	1.53	0.35	0.99	1.78	1.49
% Δi	16.9	21.3	26.4	24.2	9.2	17.8	24.2	22

Pressure of oxygen in mm.										
V.	10.	21.	31.	43.	50.	100.	150.	200.	250.	
1.33	i_D	4.06	5.57	7.62	7.21	7.55	4.8			
	i_L	3.81	4.9	5.29	5.83	5.92	3.74			
	Δi	0.25	0.67	1.70	1.38	1.63	1.06			
	% Δi	6.2	12.0	22.3	19.1	21.6	22.1			
1.47	i_D	4.47	5.92	8.06	7.94	8.06	5.29			
	i_L	4.24	5.24	6.29	6.33	6.48	4.24			
	Δi	0.23	0.68	1.77	1.61	1.58	1.05			
	% Δi	5.1	11.5	22	20.3	19.6	19.9			
1.6	i_D	4.85	6.25	8.43	8.38	8.49	6.25			
	i_L	4.69	5.70	6.78	6.75	7.00	5.1			
	Δi	0.16	0.55	1.65	1.59	1.49	1.15			
	% Δi	3.3	8.8	19.6	19.1	17.6	18.4			
1.73	i_D	5.29	6.63	8.37	8.89	8.78	7.00			
	i_L	5.15	5.92	7.00	7.21	7.55	6.16			
	Δi	0.14	0.71	1.37	1.68	1.23	0.84			
	% Δi	2.6	10.7	16.4	18.9	14.0	12.9			
1.87	i_D	5.61	6.93	8.83	9.27	9.11	8.12			
	i_L	5.48	6.33	7.48	7.81	7.94	7.00			
	Δi	0.13	0.60	1.35	1.46	1.17	1.12			
	% Δi	2.3	8.7	15.3	15.8	12.8	13.8			
2	i_D	6.08	7.18	8.92	9.75	9.38	8.60	6.25	3.87	3.32
	i_L	6.00	6.71	7.94	8.25	8.25	7.68	5.48	3.46	3.00
	Δi	0.08	0.47	0.98	1.50	1.13	0.92	0.77	0.41	0.32
	% Δi	1.3	6.5	11	15.4	12.1	10.7	12.3	10.6	9.6
2.13	i_D	6.56	7.42	9.27	10.15	9.7	9.11	7.42	4.58	3.74
	i_L	6.48	6.86	8.00	8.69	8.66	8.25	6.48	4.12	3.46
	Δi	0.08	0.56	1.27	1.45	1.04	0.86	0.94	0.46	0.28
	% Δi	1.2	7.5	13.7	14.4	10.7	9.4	12.7	10.0	7.5
2.27	i_D	7.07	8.25	9.43	10.58	9.95	9.7	8.49	5.2	4.36
	i_L	7.07	7.94	8.72	9.17	9.06	8.89	7.75	4.69	4.06
	Δi	—	0.31	0.71	1.41	0.89	0.81	0.74	0.51	0.30
	% Δi	—	3.8	7.5	13.3	8.9	8.4	8.7	9.8	6.9

TABLE I (contd.)

		Pressure of oxygen in mm.							
V.		31.	43.	50.	100.	150.	200.	250.	
2.4	i_D	9.64	10.86	10.30	10.20	9.43	5.83	5.00	
	i_L	9.08	9.59	9.43	9.49	8.66	5.48	4.69	
	Δi	0.56	1.27	0.87	0.71	0.77	0.35	0.31	
	% Δi	5.8	11.7	8.4	7	8.2	6.0	6.2	
2.53	i_D	10.1	11.40	10.73	10.86	10.24	6.86	5.66	
	i_L	9.59	10.15	10.00	10.20	9.43	6.33	5.29	
	Δi	0.51	1.25	0.73	0.66	0.81	0.53	0.37	
	% Δi	5.1	11	6.8	6.1	7.9	7.7	6.5	
2.67	i_D	10.1	11.69	11.05	11.40	10.93	7.75	6.40	
	i_L	9.8	10.52	10.40	10.77	10.2	7.00	6.00	
	Δi	0.3	1.17	0.65	0.63	0.73	0.75	0.40	
	% Δi	3	10.0	5.9	5.5	6.7	9.7	6.3	
2.8	i_D	10.4	12.04	11.40	11.96	11.64	8.54	7.17	
	i_L	10.2	11.03	10.77	11.36	10.91	8.00	6.71	
	Δi	0.2	1.01	0.63	0.60	0.73	0.54	0.43	
	% Δi	1.9	8.4	5.5	5.0	6.3	6.3	6.0	

		Pressure of oxygen in mm.										
V=2.93		V=3.07			V=3.2			V=3.33				
150. 200. 250.		150 200. 250.			150. 200. 250.			150. 200. 250.				
i_D	12.21	9.43	8.06	12.84	10.15	8.89	13.35	10.58	9.7	13.90	10.95	10.49
i_L	11.49	8.89	7.62	12.17	9.54	8.43	12.69	9.8	9.17	13.19	10.58	10.00
Δi	0.72	0.54	0.44	0.67	0.61	0.46	0.66	0.78	0.53	0.71	0.37	0.49
% Δi	5.9	5.7	5.5	5.2	6.0	5.2	4.9	7.4	5.5	5.1	3.4	4.7

TABLE II

Potential variation of the Joshi effect in oxygen at different gas pressures, with diode detection.

(Ozoniser B)

Temp. = 27°-29°. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 cyc./sec. Source of irradiation = Two 200 watt (glass) bulbs run at 200 volts, and 15 cm. from B.

		Pressure of oxygen in mm.								
V=0.67.		V=0.8.		V=0.93.		V=1.07.		V=1.2.		101.
52.		52.		52.		52.		52.		101.
i_D	3	20	89	113	1	124	24			
i_L	3	13	51	67	1	77	15			
Δi	—	7	38	46	—	47	9			
% Δi	—	35.0	42.7	40.7	—	37.9	37.5			

		Pressure of oxygen in mm.										
V=1.33.		V=1.47.			V=1.6.			V=1.73.				
52. 101.		52. 101. 148.			52. 101. 148			52. 101. 148.				
i_D	142	97	2	159	120	8	174	138	32	189	148	119
i_L	93	61	2	105	75	6	118	90	20	130	100	71
Δi	49	36	—	54	45	2	56	48	12	59	48	39
% Δi	34.5	37.1	—	34.0	37.5	25.0	32.2	34.8	37.5	31.2	32.4	35.5

		Pressure of oxygen in mm.						
V=1.87.		V=2.					V=2.	
52.		101.			148.		250.	
i_D	203	161	144	2	217	17.	167	8
i_L	139	108	91	2	153	117	105	5
Δi	64	53	53	—	64	54	62	3
% Δi	31.5	32.9	36.8	—	29.5	31.6	37.1	37.5

TABLE II (contd.)

V.	Pressure of oxygen in mm.					
	52.	101.	148.	250.	346.	456.
2.13	t_D	235	186	181	16	5
	t_L	165	131	118	10	5
	Δt	70	55	63	6	—
	$\% \Delta t$	29.8	29.6	34.8	37.5	—
2.27	t_D	245	203	192	35	8
	t_L	175	143	127	20	6
	Δt	70	60	65	15	2
	$\% \Delta t$	28.6	29.6	33.6	42.9	25.0
2.4	t_D	264	214	204	72	19
	t_L	188	152	136	42	12
	Δt	76	62	68	30	7
	$\% \Delta t$	28.8	29	33.3	41.7	36.8
2.53	t_D	274	230	221	162	27
	t_L	198	168	152	99	17
	Δt	76	62	69	63	10
	$\% \Delta t$	27.5	27	31.2	38.9	37
2.67	t_D	290	245	235	195	39
	t_L	212	170	163	124	24
	Δt	78	66	72	71	15
	$\% \Delta t$	26.9	27	30.6	36.4	38.5
2.93	t_D	314	268	264	242	78
	t_L	233	201	186	162	43
	Δt	81	67	78	80	35
	$\% \Delta t$	25.8	25	29.5	33.6	44.9
3.2	t_D	335	289	283	264	172
	t_L	253	219	203	177	105
	Δt	82	70	80	87	67
	$\% \Delta t$	24.5	24.2	28.3	32.9	39
3.47	t_D	355	309	303	302	224
	t_L	270	239	221	209	146
	Δt	85	70	82	93	78
	$\% \Delta t$	23.9	22.7	27.1	30.8	34.8
3.73	t_D	373	324	320	328	274
	t_L	285	251	237	234	185
	Δt	88	73	83	94	89
	$\% \Delta t$	23.6	22.5	26.0	28.7	32.5
4	t_D	390	341	337	359	316
	t_L	300	265	251	261	221
	Δt	90	76	86	98	95
	$\% \Delta t$	23.1	22.3	25.5	27.3	30.1
4.27	t_D	406	357	352	383	349
	t_L	313	282	264	281	248
	Δt	93	75	88	102	101
	$\% \Delta t$	22.9	21.0	25.0	26.6	28.9
4.53	t_D	420	372	368	408	376
	t_L	325	295	279	300	275
	Δt	95	77	89	108	101
	$\% \Delta t$	22.6	20.7	24.2	26.5	26.9
4.67	t_D	428	381	377	418	388
	t_L	330	303	286	308	282
	Δt	98	78	91	110	110
	$\% \Delta t$	22.7	20.5	24.1	26.3	26.3
34	V = 4.8		V = 5.07		V = 5.33	
	t_D	439	345	474	371	411
	t_L	330	235	360	255	308
	Δt	109	110	114	116	103
$\% \Delta t$	24.8	31.9	24.1	31.3	25.1	

DISCUSSION

That the minimum 'threshold potential' V_m is an important determinant of the rate and nature of a chemical or quasi-chemical change in gaseous systems under electrical

FIG. 2
Potential variation of the Joshi effect in oxygen at different gas pressures, with vacuo-junction detection (ozoniser A).

discharge, has been observed by Joshi (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 118, 137; *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1931, Part III, Chem. Sec., Abst No. 63; *Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548; 1946, 18, 281; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 389). This V_m may be related simply to the corresponding Paschen potential, especially in elementary gases. It is marked by a sudden increase in the current through, and the wattage dissipated

in, the system. From the $V-i$ characteristics in Fig. 3 (cf. Table II) it is seen that at first, i is but small and increases slowly with V . The breakdown of the gas as a dielectric is well marked above V_m , as shown by the noticeably large current rise for a given voltage increase. Thus e. g., i_b for ozoniser A filled with oxygen at 43 mm. is undetected at 0.67 kV (Table I). Above this potential, it rises rapidly, to 3.74 at 0.8 kV, and 5.66 at 0.93 kV. For ozoniser B at 346 mm. (Table II), i_b is 5 at 2.13 kV, increases slowly to 78 at 2.93 kV and thence rapidly to 172 at 3.2 kV. The 'threshold potential' V_m for oxygen in ozoniser B, obtained by extrapolation of the corresponding $V-i_b$ characteristic curves in Fig. 3, is sensibly a linear function of the gas pressure p

FIG. 3

Potential variation of the Joshi effect in oxygen at different gas pressures, with diode detection (ozoniser B).

over a fairly wide range (Fig. 4). This also obtains with the Paschen potential. The increase of V_m , as of the Paschen potential, with p results from the increased number of encounters with molecules of an ion or/and electron in the inter-electrode space.

It is a general finding of Joshi (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 22A, 389) that well below V_m , when the conduction is mainly capacitative, Δi does not occur despite the use of intense and even short-wave radiations and large displacement currents obtained, say, with high frequencies input to the system (Joshi and Lad, *ibid.*, 1945, 22A, 293). Furthermore, whilst $\% \Delta i$ is maximum near V_m and decreases with V , the net effect Δi increases initially and decreases thereafter. As will be seen from Fig. 3 (*cf.* also Table II), apparently Δi in oxygen sets in below V_m^* as defined above. It rises near this potential followed by a slow rise with V afterwards (Figs. 2 and 3. *cf.* Tables I and II); at still higher V , however, it is reduced (Fig. 2. *cf.* Table I). Thus *e. g.*, V_m for $pO_2 = 250$ mm. in ozoniser B is 2.23 kV. The effect at this pressure is just detectable at 2 kV (Table II). Δi increases rapidly from 3 at 2 kV to 71 at 2.67 kV and slowly afterwards to 110 at 4.67 kV. As suggested by the $\Delta i-V$ curves in Fig. 2, it is important to emphasise that the increase in Δi with V is distributed over a wider range of V at higher than at lower gas pressures. Thus, whilst at $pO_2 = 21$ mm., Δi reaches a maximum (of 1.78) at 0.8 kV and decreases thereafter, at 250 mm. it is still increasing at 3.33 kV. The subsequent fall in Δi with V is not noticeable in Fig. 3 up to the maximum potential applied, *viz.*, 4.67 kV for pressures 52, 101, 148 and 250 mm., and 5.33 kV at 346 and 456 mm.

The relative effect $\% \Delta i$ is but small below V_m , increases rapidly with V and attains a maximum near V_m (Fig. 3). Above this potential it decreases (Figs. 2 and 3). Thus *e. g.*, V_m for $pO_2 = 346$ mm. in ozoniser B is 2.73 kV. The relative effect, $\% \Delta i$ increases from 25.0 at 2.27 kV to 44.9 at 2.93 kV and decreases with further increase in V to 24.1 at 5.33 kV (Table II). As will be evident from the $\% \Delta i-V$ curves in Figs. 2 and 3, the variation with V of $\% \Delta i$ is more gradual at higher than at lower gas pressures. The comparatively flat distribution over a given voltage range, both of Δi and $\% \Delta i$, especially at higher gas pressures, as shown by the corresponding curves in Figs. 2 and 3, has significance for a general theory of this Δi phenomenon and its dependence on the gas pressure.

It is instructive to consider Δi values at constant i_b for various gas pressures as read off from the ordinates of the i_b and i_c curves in Figs. 2 and 3. That when so considered Δi for oxygen in ozoniser A increases with p up to a limiting pressure, *viz.* 43 mm. and then decreases is evident from results (deduced from $V-i$ curves in Fig. 2) cited herein under.

$pO_2(\text{mm.})$ $i_b = 8$	10	21	31	43	50	100	150	200	250
Δi	0.0	0.35	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.05	0.8	0.6	0.45
$\% \Delta i$	0.0	4.4	18.8	20.0	18.8	13.1	10.0	7.5	5.6

In the case of ozoniser B, which had a greater electrode separation and a consequent concentration of the field near the surface of the inner electrode, Δi at constant i_b continues to increase with p up to even the largest value used, *viz.*, 456 mm. This is seen from the following results obtained from $V-i$ curves in Fig. 3.

$p_{O_2}(\text{mm.})$ $i_D=200$	52	101	148	250	346	456
Δi	62	58	65	72	73	83
% Δi	32	29	32.5	35.5	36.5	41.5

The above difference in the pressure influence of Δi and % Δi in ozonisers A and B might also originate from the difference in the nature of the detector employed.

FIG. 4

Variation with gas pressure of threshold potential V_m of oxygen.

Joshi (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1946, Part III, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst. No. 26; 1947, *Phys. Sec.*, Abst.; *Curr. Sci.*, 1946, 18, 281; 1947, 16, 19) has suggested the formation, under discharge, of an adsorption-like ionic+molecular electrode layer as primary to Δi . Photo-electrons emitted from this boundary layer are captured by the electronegative elements in the discharge space forming slow moving negative ions which reduce i by a space charge effect. The electron affinity of the oxygen atom is about 3.80 e. v. (as compared with that of fluorine 3.94, chlorine 3.70, bromine 3.54, and iodine 3.22) (Glockler, *Phys. Rev.*, 1934, 48, III); that of the oxygen molecule is 2.7 (Weiss, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 966). The appreciably high Δi observed in oxygen is therefore to be anticipated. The probability of electron capture depends upon p/E , where p is the gas pressure and E , the applied field. Increase of Δi with p and decrease with V follow, as observed.

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to Professor S. S. Joshi for suggesting the problem, and for his kind interest and valuable guidance.

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Received April 29, 1948.